

DIPLOMA

TA'LIM FIDOYILARI

RESPUBLIKA ILMIY JURNALIDA

Ismatillaeva Sitora Sayfidinnovna

KIDS TRAVEL- A WEBSITE FOR CHILDREN'S TOURISM IN UZBEKISTAN

NOMLI MAQOLASI BILAN ISHTIROK ETGANI UCHUN TAQDIRLANADI

Bosh muharrir:
A.A. Abdurahmonov

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★ ★ ★ ★ ★
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MENTION
★ ★ ★ ★ ★

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